

THE STYLISTIC DEVICES IN TRANSLATING ROBERT M. DRAKE'S "BEAUTIFUL AND DAMNED" WORK FROM ENGLISH TO UZBEK

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10287171>

Abstract. This article is about the stylistic devices encountered in the literal translation of the work "Beautiful and damned" written by Robert M. Drake and their analysis. This article also provides information about some stylistic devices that occur in translation.

Key words: phonetic stylistic devices, onomatopoeia, syntactical stylistic devices, inversion, aposiopesis, lexical stylistic devices, interjection.

СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИЕМЫ ПРИ ПЕРЕВОДЕ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ РОБЕРТА М. ДРЕЙКА «КРАСИВЫЕ И ПРОКЛЯТЫЕ» С АНГЛИЙСКОГО НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ

Аннотация. Статья посвящена стилистическим приемам, встречающимся при дословном переводе произведения Роберта М. Дрейка «Прекрасные и проклятые», и их анализу. В этой статье также представлена информация о некоторых стилистических приемах, встречающихся при переводе.

Ключевые слова: фонетико-стилистические приемы, ономотопея, синтаксически-стилистические приемы, инверсия, апозиопезис, лексико-стилистические приемы, междометие.

INTRODUCTION

The "Beautiful and Damned" by Robert M. Drake is both a heartbreaking and beautiful little story of love and loss, strength and finding your way. This impressive and superb novel will keep you up for many days and nights as it tells a great story for the reader of all ages. There are some stylistic devices in literal translation of work "Beautiful and Damned" written by Robert M. Drake.

METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

Some stylistic devices were used in translation of this article from English to Uzbek.

There are three stylistic devices:

1. phonetic stylistic devices
2. syntactical stylistic devices
3. lexical stylistic devices

Phonetic stylistic devices: onomatopoeia

Onomatopoeia is usually defined as a sequence of sounds (a word) which imitates non-verbal sounds produced in nature by things, people or animals.

"Okay." He didn't think much of her silence. He just kept on driving as he hummed a sweet little jazz number.

The word "hummed" is an onomatopoeia. This word imitates the sound of sing.

He looked out his rear view mirror and accelerated a little.

There is an onomatopoeia. The verb "accelerated" imitates speed up.

Her heart fluttered. "And okay, I'll remember her name and I'll get back to you on that."

The word "fluttered" is an onomatopoeia. This word imitates diastole. So, we can use this word as onomatopoeic word.

Her hands clapped, and her left foot pressed against the base of James car.

In this sentence has two onomatopoeic words. Firstly, the word "clapped" is an onomatopoeic word. Because it is the sound of hands. Secondly, the verb "pressed" is the sound of foot.

His words carefully exited his lips and his eyes tensed a little as if he had something else to say.

The word "tensed" is an onomatopoeic word, because it imitates eyes.

The stylistic side of translation (and writing to some extent) plays one of the biggest roles in providing readership with a proper equivalent of fiction.

Stylistic inversion is usually defined as an intentional change of a typical word order in an utterance, the aim of which is to attract the attention of the reader.

"I'm kidding, you know you can't find a decent cup of coffee anywhere in the city." He smiled again.

The writer attracted the word "kidding" to the attention of the reader.

"Shoot, I left my car at work! Shoot! Her hands clapped, and her left foot pressed against the base of James car.

The writer attracted the word "shoot" to the attention of the reader.

"Some matches", he said as he took an old box of matches out and lit the cigarette up.

The writer attracted the word "some matches" to the attention of the reader.

"Prodigly," he said as his head rocked back and forth.

Syntactical stylistic devices: aposiopesis

Aposiopesis, also known as break-in-the narrative, aims at intentionally breaking off parts of the sentence to convey emotionality of the speaker.

"That sounds like fun. I hope you enjoy yourself." She took a few steps closer to the cashier.

"Yeah... I hope so, too."

The word "yeah..." is an aposiopesis. Here the author omits the second part of the phrase, which is rather easy to predict.

"Angela..." he said as Billie Holiday played is the backdrop.

The word "Angela..." is an aposiopesis

"Hello," said a woman on the other end.

"Hello..." said James.

The word "Hello..." is an aposiopesis

"Because ever since I saw you, I knew, and I knew I would find you. To tell you..."

The sentence "to tell you..." is an aposiopesis

Lexical stylistic devices: interjection

Interjections are a means to represent spoken language variety in literature as they mostly deal with the emotions of the speakers expressed by either or longer words in the course of speech.

"I got one!" he shouted in victory as if he had just won a contest.

"Got what?"

“Some matches,” he said as he took an old box of matches out and lit the cigarette up.

The sentence “Got what?” is an interjection.

“Scarlett!” He approached her from the middle of the street.

Lexical stylistic devices: euphemism is a stylistic device which aims at re-naming an unpleasant or unacceptable word.

“Oh God, this was clearly a mistake. I’m so sorry for asking.” She quickly turned away and fumbled to open the car door.

Religious euphemisms are very common. The word “Oh God” is a religious euphemism.

“Shoot, I left my car at work! Shoot! Her hands clapped, and her left foot pressed against the base of James car.

The word “shoot” is euphemism.

CONCLUSION

Translation as such is a demanding task which requires the translator be able to tackle many issues that arise during the process.

In order to successfully convey the intended ideas the translator has to take stylistics into consideration as this branch of linguistics plays a big role in presenting a natural and understandable equivalent of the original book to readership.

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